

Development of a Low-cost Portable Tropical Almond (*Terminalia catappa*) Decorticator

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Abstract

Tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa*) is a drupe which is nutritionally rich but underutilized tree nut, mainly grown in tropical and coastal regions. Despite its potential, processing remains a challenge due to its hard shell encasing the kernel, and the lack of suitable mechanical solutions for shell removal. Tropical almonds, despite their nutritional and economic value, pose significant post-harvest challenges due to their hard shells, which require labour-intensive and inefficient manual processing. The developed machine consists of two roller having grooved surfaces, one of the rollers on which power is applied also have spikes and teeth on it. The machine is connected to a 1 HP AC motor using a V- belt. The breaking of husk and hard shell of almond is carried out by beating and cutting action of spike fitted on one roller. The operating speed of motor fitted in machine is 1450 rpm. Before fabrication of machine some physical properties of the nuts such as size, bulk density (208.88 kg/m³) and angle of repose (51.54°), were measured to decide design parameters such as clearance between rollers, hopper dimensions, angle of slant part of hopper etc. Performance tests revealed a throughput capacity of 4.28 kg/hr, whole kernel recovery of 31% and broken kernel percentage is 69%. The total fabrication cost was approximately ₹15,000 making it an affordable solution for rural and marginal farmers. The machine offers a promising alternative for decentralized almond processing in tropical and economically constrained settings.

Keywords: Decorticator, Kernel recovery, Portable machine, Tropical Almond

Introduction

Tropical almond (*Terminalia catappa*), also referred to as Indian almond, is valued for its edible seeds, medicinal bark, and ecological

benefits in coastal stabilization. Despite its abundance and nutritional value (21 g protein and 49 g fat per 100 g) (Okafor, J.C. 1989), its commercial utilization is minimal in India. One

of the major limiting factors is the lack of affordable machinery for cracking the extremely hard outer shell of the nut. Shelling is generally performed manually, resulting in low productivity and high labor intensity. While automated almond shellers exist for *Prunus dulcis* (sweet almond), these machines are unsuitable for *T. catappa* due to differences in shell hardness, shape, and kernel fragility. Therefore, a specialized and economical mechanical sheller is essential for small-scale

operations, particularly in regions where tropical almonds grow abundantly.

The tropical almond consists of Epicarp a thin layer of skin at the outer most part of the almond, Mesocarp (hull) it's a fleshy and fibrous part of the fruit just like a coconut located between skin and shell, Endocarp (shell) hard shell that surrounds and protect the seed and at the inner most part of the almond it has kernel (seed).

Fig. No. 1. Tropical almond after sun dried for 90 days after harvesting

Fig No. 2. Components of Tropical almond

This research aimed to design, fabricate and evaluate a tropical almond decorticator suitable for use by low-income/local farmers and micro-enterprises. The goals included enhancing post-harvest

processing efficiency, reducing human drudgery and promoting the economic utilization of otherwise neglected crop. The objectives of this study were to develop a low-cost portable tropical almond decorticator. For designing of this machine some of the physical properties of almond were also measured.

Methodology

The process of decorticating tropical almonds involves a systematic sequence of operation for getting efficient decortication with higher kernel recovery and reducing physical effort. It follows as Harvesting the almond is harvested when its fully, redish brown color and have sweet aroma followed by cleaning removing any unnecessary material or waste, Drying almond for 90 days to remove moisture from almond for easy decortication, Grading process of classifying and separating the almond based on their size, after grading the almonds are feed to machine for decortication and followed by separation of kernel and broken shell manually.

Fig No. 03. Processing flow chart of Tropical almond

Determination of physical properties of tropical almond.

Physical properties are essential for determining the size of hopper, angle of hopper, clearance between the rollers, collecting screen and moisture content during the operation.

Size and weight were determined using vernier calliper and electrical weighing machine respectively.

Determining the angle of repose: - The angle of repose (θ , deg.) is determined by using an open-ended cylinder of 15 cm diameter and 50 cm height. The cylinder was filled with nut and the cylinder was slowly raised until it formed a heap of cone on the circular plate. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula (Karababa, 2006):

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{2H}{D} \right)$$

where, H is height of the cone (cm),
 D is the diameter of circular plate.

Determining the Bulk density: - The bulk density is determined by measuring the weight and volume of tropical almond sample. First the weight of the empty container W_1 (in grams) was recorded. Pouring almonds into the container until it is full to the marked volume. Avoid shaking or compacting the almonds; pour gently for loose bulk density. Record the weight W_2 . Calculating the total mass of container and subtracting the mass of empty cylinder. Then we use the known volume of the container (V) and calculated the bulk density. (Sahay, K.M., & Singh, K.K. 2004).

$$\text{Bulk Density} = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{V} \times 100$$

Fabrication of tropical almond decorticator.

The machine was fabricated using mild steel for durability and cost-effectiveness. Major components include:

1. Supporting Frame: The supporting frame is made by using angle iron and metal strips.
2. Hopper: Rectangular metal sheet was used to prepare a hopper of capacity 4.9 kg.
3. Decortication Unit: It consists of two rollers having grooved surfaces, one plain rollers and other Spike -square bar roller is fitted on a frame. The clearance between the two rollers is adjustable.
4. Power Unit: 1 HP electric motor (1440).
5. Transmission: V-belt and pulley system is used to transmit power from motor to decortication unit.
6. Collection Tray/Screen: The collecting screen/tray is made up of wire mesh screen.

Figure 4: Decortication Unit of machine

Figure 5: Tropical Almond decorticator

Performance evaluation of tropical almond decorticator.

The performance of tropical almond decorticator was measured using following formulae:

- (i) **The kernel to whole nut percentage;** It describes the percentage of kernel present in whole nut.

$$\text{Kernel to whole nut percentage} = \frac{\text{average weight of recovered kernel}}{\text{average weight of whole nut input}} \times 100\%$$

- (ii) **The kernel recovery efficiency (decortication efficiency):** It is expressed as percentage of weight of recovered kernel to the weight of potential kernel material.

$$\text{Kernel recovery efficiency} = \frac{\text{weight of all recovered kernel}}{\text{weight of potential kernel material}} \times 100\%$$

- (iii) **The proportion of whole kernel:** It is expressed as percentage of weight of recovered whole kernel to the weight of all recovered kernel.

$$\text{Proportion of whole kernel} = \frac{\text{weight of recovered whole kernel}}{\text{weight of all recovered kernel}} \times 100\%$$

- (iv) **The proportion of broken kernel:** It is expressed as percentage of weight of particular substandard kernel to the weight of all recovered kernel.

$$\text{Proportion of broken kernel} = \frac{\text{weight of particular substandard kernel}}{\text{weight of all recovered kernel}} \times 100\%$$

The weight of substandard kernel is the broken or damaged or shrivelled kernel after machine decortication. The weight of all recovered kernel includes all the kernel (whole and broken) recovered after machine decortication. (Pinson, G.S., Melville, D.J. and Cox, D.R.S.) (1991).

Results and Discussion

The physical properties of almond were measured. The average size of almond was found to be 72.81 mm, 41.54 mm and 32.54 mm respectively. Its average weight is 15.69 gm.

Table 1: Cost of construction of machine

Parts & Component	Description	Price (₹)
Mild Steel Frame	50mm × 50mm angle iron, welding	2500
Iron Rollers (with spikes)	Lathe-turned steel rod, Spikes fitted	2500
Bearing	4 UPC-204 bearing	900
V-Belt & Pulleys	For power transmission	600
Electric Motor	1 Hp, Three-phase, 1440 RPM	4000
Hopper and Collecting unit	Mild Steel and Wire mesh	500
Miscellaneous cost	Fabrication charges, nuts and bolts, paint etc.	4000
Total	₹15,000	

Conclusion.

The tropical almond decorticator developed is a low-cost, small-scale mechanical solution which can be used for improving the almond shelling operations in rural areas and increasing their income. The machine was able to process dried tropical almonds at a modest capacity of 4.28 kg/hour, with significant labour savings compared to traditional hand cracking methods. The shelling efficiency, whole kernel recovery and kernel breaking percentage is found to be 70%, 31% and 69% respectively.

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The bulk density and angle of repose of almond was found to be 208.88kg/m³ & 51.54° respectively. The capacity of machine is 4.28 kg/hr. The kernel to whole nut percentage of tropical almond was found to be 4.19%. The performance of machine was measured in terms of kernel recovery efficiency, whole kernel percentage & broken kernel percentage which was found to be 70%, 31% and 69% respectively. The cost of construction of Tropical almond decorticator is given below:

Crops: 1492 from a Different Perspective. FAO.

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